

THE ROLE OF HOTEL BUSINESS IN DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM INDUSTRY

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Abstract. This article discusses the role and advantages of hotel industry in the sphere of tourism. In current conditions, there is a competitive environment in the field of tourism, the market despite the complexity of their relations, a number of tourism companies in Uzbekistan and hotels are being established, but most of them are from a certain time then, unable to cope with the competition, it leaves the tourism market. Hotels are not only an important type of economic activity enterprises, but also a complex organizational structure characterized by the distribution of management goals and tasks between departments and specific employees. All about these are discussed in this article.

Keywords: tourism industry, hotel management, economy, infrastructure, restaurants, tour operator service, tourist

TURIZM INDUSTURASINI RIVOJLANISHDA MEHMONXONA BIZNESINING O'RNI.

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada mehmonxona industriyasining turizm sohasidagi o'rni va afzalliklari muhokama qilinadi. Hozirgi sharoitda turizm sohasida raqobat muhiti mavjud bo'lib, bozor munosabatlari murakkab bo'lishiga qaramay, O'zbekistonda bir qator sayyohlik kompaniyalari va mehmonxonalar tashkil

etilmoqda, biroq ularning aksariyati ma’lum bir davridan buyon faoliyat yurita olmayapti. Raqobatga dosh bera olsa ham, k’opgina joylashtirish korxonolari turizm bozorini tark etadi. Mehmonxonalar nafaqat korxonalarining iqtisodiy faoliyatining muhim turi, balki boshqaruv maqsadlari va vazifalarini bo’limlar va aniq xodimlar o’rtasida taqsimlash bilan tavsiflangan murakkab tashkiliy tuzilmadir. Bularning barchasi haqida ushbu maqolada muhokama qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: turizm sanoati, mehmonxona boshqaruvi, iqtisodiyot, infratuzilma, restoranlar, turoperator xizmati, turist.

РОЛЬ ГОСТИНИЧНОГО БИЗНЕСА В РАЗВИТИИ ТУРИСТИЧЕСКОЙ ИНДУСТРИИ

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Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются роль и преимущества гостиничного хозяйства в сфере туризма. В нынешних условиях в сфере туризма сложилась конкурентная среда, на рынке, несмотря на сложность их взаимоотношений, создается ряд туристических компаний Узбекистана и гостиниц, но большинство из них с определенного времени не в состоянии справиться с конкуренцией, уходит с туристического рынка. Гостиницы представляют собой не только важный вид хозяйственной деятельности предприятий, но и сложную организационную структуру, характеризующуюся распределением целей и задач управления между подразделениями и конкретными работниками. Обо всем этом и пойдет речь в этой статье.

Ключевые слова: индустрия туризма, гостиничный менеджмент, экономика, инфраструктура, рестораны, тuroperatorские услуги, турист.

Entrance. Tourism is one of the most promising and rapidly developing sectors of the economy. Tourism is the main type of activity that has a significant impact on economic growth and employment in the country, as it affects transport, hotel and restaurant services, trade, construction, consumer goods and several sectors of the economy.

Providing services in our country since the first days of independence tourism services as a priority direction of economic development was interpreted, and attention to it was raised to the level of state policy. For the development of the industry the necessary organizational and legal mechanisms have been created by the government relevant regulatory documents have been adopted and work in this direction is still ongoing continues.

In the current conditions, there is a competitive environment in the field of tourism, the market despite the complexity of their relations, a number of tourism companies in Uzbekistan and hotels are being established, but most of them are from a certain time then, unable to cope with the competition, it leaves the tourism market. Statistics according to data, in 2022, 959 hotels were operating in the republic if comparing with 2011 their number was 254 and 3139 guest houses catered to internal and international tourists in 2022.²

Tourism and the hotel industry are always side by side, and the adequacy of hotels also contributes greatly to the economy of the region and brings many facts. The existence of a hotel alone is not enough to develop regional tourism.

There some important aspects of the hotel industry are as:

- It generates Income
- It generates employment
- It is a source of foreign exchange earnings
- Developing Infrastructure
- It promotes peace & stability
- Increases government revenue

² Speech of the Ministry of Tourism and Cultural Heritage of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Deputy Minister of Tourism and Cultural Heritage - B. Shakhriyurov. investment@uzbektourism.uz www.uzbektourism.uz

- It improves the quality of life of locals
- It provides recreational facilities

Hotels are not only an important type of economic activity enterprises, but also a complex organizational structure characterized by the distribution of management goals and tasks between departments and specific employees. The organizational structure of management means a set of management links that are located in a subordinate manner and provide communication between the managing and managed systems.³ The organizational structure of management is the composition, interrelationship, location and is formed from their interactions. The establishment of such a structure first of all implies the distribution of rights and responsibilities between certain departments of the organization. The following components are distinguished in the hotel management structure: management links (departments), management levels (steps) and management relationships - horizontal and vertical relationships. Management links include structural departments of the hotel, as well as certain specialists who perform the relevant management functions or some of them (for example, managers who regulate and coordinate the activities of several structural departments).

An example of a hotel's strategic goal, which is determined by the owner of each hotel, can be the orientation of the enterprise to a certain segment of the market, for example: group tourists or individual travelers, tourists trying to relax and restore health, or congresses and service to conference participants. To develop a strategic goal, a hotel owner can determine that the restaurant in the hotel complex serves only its guests.

Also, in accordance with the main purpose of the enterprise, a certain level of prices can be set for accommodation in the hotel. Such decisions and tasks fall into enterprise, the choice of a place for its construction, its architecture and interior, furniture, equipment, Personnel Selection will depend on these decisions and tasks. In international experience, a standard description of tourist accommodation facilities

³ Ch. Medoy. Tourism of management. 2013.

developed by the World Tourism Organization (WTO) has been adopted. According to him, placement tools are divided into collective and individual categories (Table 1)

According to WTO experts, collective placement tools are an object that provides the traveler with a place to rest. In this case, the living space must reach at least one family and be in a single commercial management.

The hotel industry is a unique economic complex, it has its own production culture, which can affect the good or bad side of the culture, for example, on production, workers on their personnel, legal staff, personal affairs . When complaints about service are received, the reasonable remedy remains to investigate the culprit, not the cause. The knowledge and skills of the manager of the hotel organization should be perfect in all respects, and should be wider than the scope of knowledge about some of his activities.

Table 1

Standard Classification of tourist accommodation facilities⁴

<i>categories</i>	<i>types</i>	<i>groups</i>
<i>1. Collective placement tools</i>	<i>1.1. Hotels</i>	<i>1.1.1. Hotels. 1.1.2. Similar business</i>
	<i>1.2. Cpecial enterprises</i>	<i>1.2.1. Healthcare facilities 1.2.2. Holiday camps 1.2.3. Public transport 1.2.4. Congress halls</i>
	<i>1.3. Other community enterprises</i>	<i>1.3.1. Vocation homes 1.3.2. Camping 1.3.3. Others</i>
<i>2. Indual placement tools</i>	<i>2.1. Individual placement tools</i>	<i>2.1.1. Private homes 2.1.2. Rented 2.1.3. Rented house 2.1.4. Living with relatives free 2.1.5. Others</i>

⁴ WTO World Tourism Barometer. Madrid. WTO.2017

Currently, this model has been in depression for the last 25 years from the global hotel services market for 2 million dollars in the style of "pales" rooms in love from finished. The second model is associated with the name of the American entrepreneur Kemons Wilson (Hotel system “Holiday Inn”) in which, along with a high level of Service, great importance is attached to satisfying the wishes of the client. The hotel system, established on the basis of this model, has the following basic requirements:

1. Style unit (architecture, interior).
 2. The unity of indicators and external information.
 3. Spacious and functional case.
 4. Speed of customer registration.
 5. Availability of rooms designed for regular customers.
 6. Breakfast "Swedish table".
 7. Conference-availability of HAL.
 8. Flexible system of tariffs.
 9. Unified management, marketing and communication service.
- Currently, 50% of hotel rooms in the world belong to the second model.

Table 2.

World leading hotel systems

<u>Name of company</u>	The country where the headquartes are located	Number of rooms
Hospitality Franchise system Blanstone Part	USA	490000
Holiday Inn World Wide	England	386323
Best Western International	USA	295305
Accor	France	279145
Choice Hotel International	USA	271812
Mariott International	USA	251425
Itt Sheraton Corp.	USA	130528
Promus Corp.	USA	105930
Hilton Hotel Corp.	USA	101000
Carlson Hospitality World Wide	USA	91177

As for the hotel business of our country, today there are 97 requirements for establishing a hotel in our country, and 138 requirements for receiving a "star".

As a result, out of 1,165 hotels in our country, there are only 40 "star" hotels, of which only 4 are "five" and 15 are "four-star".

There are no "star" hotels in Karakalpakstan, Jizzakh, Kashkadarya and Fergana, and only 1 in Andijan, Navoi, Syrdarya and Tashkent regions. Or, the price of staying in a hotel for one night is on average 35-40 dollars in our country, which is 20-25% more expensive than in developed countries.⁵

The fact that the accommodation has good conditions, the environment is peaceful, and the services provided to customers are at a high level have a great influence on the customers' use of hotel services. This puts them on a level playing field with larger enterprises, as foreign tourists often have soft feelings towards local products and familiar services offered by start-ups and micro-entrepreneurs.

One of the most significant and vital things about the hospitality industry is that it gives a unique service that is important to the tourism sector. Hospitality educates you on how to properly supervise and manage guests, and how to go the extra mile to satisfy guests.

Our country has a good infrastructure for the development of the hospitality industry. Our people usually study by highlighting the existing shortcomings in the field, but the tourism infrastructure in our territory of Uzbekistan is well established. Due to the growth of the industry, it is allowed for the governments to see the necessary products to improve the roads and transport services, which paves the way for the safety and security of the economic capital.

Based on the analyzed data, it is felt that there is a demand and supply gap between hotels and tourism industry in Uzbekistan and an urgent need for more hotels over time. Tourists naturally experience a shortage of available hotels, which is especially evident in the area where festivals, conventions, international conferences are organized, and the need for standard budget hotels is very high. Currently, there is

⁵ Speech of the Ministry of Tourism and Cultural Heritage of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Deputy Minister of Tourism and Cultural Heritage - B. Shakhriyurov. investment@uzbektourism.uz www.uzbektourism.uz

an urgent need for budget and mid-market hotels in Uzbekistan, which will add more budget options for all types of tourists and also add value to the tourism sector. It is very important to solve the existing problem taking into account the above points.

Conclusion and suggestions

- We need to increase additional services in our hotels.
- The main of them is the currency exchange service, which is always encountered by tourists. They should have the opportunity to exchange their currency for Uzbek soums at any time.
- The most attentive treatment of a guest has a great impact on his morale. The more quickly and qualitatively the service requested by the client is performed, the more the client will want to visit the hotel again and the hotel will have its regular client.

In most cases, there are no serious requirements for service staff, but this does not mean that everyone can find a job in a hotel or hotel. For example, knowledge of a foreign language is often required, which is already a feature of working in the hotel business. Here, education plays a very important role, because building or organizing a successful hotel requires training. At the same time, the presence of a hotel business diploma does not guarantee successful work for a graduate, because the employer has not only the "shell", but also the practical skills, knowledge and skills of a potential employee. Many hotel courses are offered for this purpose.

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